

BIOSENSOR CREATED BY IMMOBILISATION OF UREASE ON NYLON MEMBRANE IN AISE FOR DETERMINATION OF UREA IN WIDELY CONSUMED COFFEE IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Coffee, following tea, is widely regarded as the most commonly consumed non-alcoholic caffeinated beverage. A biosensor was developed by immobilising the urease enzyme onto a nylon membrane and subsequently attaching it to an ammonium ion selective electrode (AISE). The AISE was characterised using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM), revealing particle sizes ranging from 0.09 μ m to 0.49 μ m in diameter. The biosensor exhibited its optimal response within a time frame of 20 seconds at a pH of 5.5, with a urea concentration of 0.05 mM in a sodium phosphate buffer solution, while maintaining a temperature of 40°C. The device demonstrated a high level of sensitivity, with a value of 38 mV/decade. Additionally, it achieved a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.001 mM, and a linear range spanning from 0.001 to 0.80 mM. The analytical recovery of added urea was determined to be 99.8%, 101.04%, 108.35%, 103.9%, 98.99%, 104.7%, 99.93%, 102.34%, 101.76%, and 103.02%. The average concentration of urea in coffee is 0.133 mg/L, while the average pH is 5.36.

Key Words: Coffee, Urease, Urea, Biosensor, AISE, Immobilization

1. Introduction:

Coffee, manufactured from roasted and ground seeds of tropical evergreen African coffee plants, is famous. Coffee, tea, and water are the three most consumed drinks globally. It is one among the most profitable commodities worldwide. Seeds in bush fruits are thought to have originated in equatorial Africa, Java, Sumatra, Dutch East Indies, West Indies, India, and China. They also flourished naturally in African woods, notably Madagascar and Mauritius (previously one of the Mascarene Islands). The globally consumed beverage is made by roasting, grinding, and boiling green coffee beans. [1]

Coffee is vital to the economies of over 50 countries. Coffee, from the Rubiaceae genus *Coffea*, was traditionally supposed to have originated in tropical Africa. The four *Coffea* genus parts are *Agrocoffea*, *Paracoffea*, *Mascarocoffea*, and *Eucoffea*. *Coffea canephora* and *arabica* are the main commercial species. Except for *C. arabica*, which is tetraploid ($2n=4x=44$), other species are diploid ($2n=2x=22$). Compared to other species, *Coffea arabica* exhibits low polymorphism. Caffeine is the most important component in coffee beans, ranging from 0.8% to 1.4% in *Arabica* and 1.7% to 4.0% in *canephora*. Coffee beans include cellulose, minerals, carbs, lipids, tannin, and polyphenols. Low temperatures harm coffee seeds and affect storage. Since abscisic acid (ABA) promotes dormancy and hinders germination, priming seeds improves germination uniformity for crop establishment. Shade increases coffee bean weight, size, antioxidant activity, total phenolic content, and chlorogenic acid concentration, according to Adepoju (2017)[2].

The International Coffee Organisation reports increased worldwide coffee consumption and a range of beverages made from roasted coffee beans [3]. Ground coffee, called a "dose," is used to make a drink. The appropriate quantity of coffee is crucial. This grinding number impacts extraction and beverage quality, thus it must be constant. Smaller beans are needed for a homogeneous powder. To make soluble and emulsifying additives easier to incorporate into the brew, increase the extraction surface, or water-coffee interface [4]. The brewing method, recipe, and extraction of caffeine and other bioactive compounds affect the quantity [5]. Coffee powder is made using special grinders. Flat and conical burr grinders are used in homes and factories. Conical grinders have two conical rings within each other, whereas flat burr grinders have two flat rings parallel. Both versions use a motor to spin one ring while fixing the other. Certain on-demand systems employ an accumulation tank for ground powder instead of a dosage mechanism.

Ground coffee powder has different-sized granules. A particle size curve represents granules. The "first modal" is the high peak and the "second modal" the low peak. A particle might be a few micrometres or a thousand. Hot water dissolves chemicals and releases volatiles, giving coffee its unique scent [6]. An advanced biosensing approach was used to measure the urea concentration in many low-cost Indian coffee brands. Urea, a natural chemical, is frequently used unscrupulously to make coffee beans smell fresh. Research sought to illuminate possible adulteration and its effects on consumers. The research carefully examined each coffee sample using biosensing to determine urea amounts among brands. This study helps ensure the quality and authenticity of inexpensive coffee in India, so customers may enjoy their favourite drink with confidence.

Research into urea, which is abundant in nature, is essential for agricultural chemistry, food science, environmental monitoring, and medicine [7]. Urea, a water-soluble molecule with two nitrogen atoms, is a

byproduct of nitrogen and protein metabolism and weighs 60 g/mol [8]. It is a colourless, odourless solid that is water-soluble, non-acidic, and practically non-toxic [9,10]. Several species manufacture it as a byproduct of the urea cycle. Most foods contain urea, which elevates blood urea. This research measures coffee urea using a biosensor. Urea is broken down by dinickel enzyme urease (EC 3.5.1.5) into ammonia (NH₃) and carbonic acid (H₂CO₃) via carbamic acid (H₂NCOOH) (Fig. 1). In water, bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) and ammonium (NH₄⁺) ions balance carbonic acid and NH₃. Urease is produced by invertebrates, fungus, bacteria, and plants, and most species are structurally and functionally identical. In the urease active site, carbamylated lysine and hydroxyl groups link two Ni²⁺ ions. [11]

Figure 1: Schematic Breakdown of Urea by Urease in Its Byproducts

Researchers have measured beverage urea content using several ways. Colourimetric methods like the Berthelot Reaction and Diacetyl Monoxime Method and urease-based tests are historical. These approaches developed into amperometric analysis, ion-selective electrodes, LC-MS, Capillary Electrophoresis, and NMR. This historical viewpoint shows that certain beverage analysis procedures are still relevant.

Potentiometry using polymeric membrane ion-selective electrodes (ISEs) is a common method for measuring critical electrolytes. Potentiometric urea determination has various benefits over other analytical procedures, making it a favoured option in certain situations. Its exceptional sensitivity allows it to quantify even trace urea amounts in samples. This feature is useful for measuring trace urea levels accurately. Potentiometric sensors may also be designed for high urea selectivity, eliminating sample interference and assuring results dependability and accuracy. The non-destructive nature of this approach preserves the material for future studies. It can examine liquids and solids and is fast and simple for regular analyses and high-throughput applications. Potentiometric determination is adaptable and eco-friendly in analytical chemistry due to its cost-effectiveness, little chemical waste, and real-time monitoring [12].

Since ammonium ion concentration is important for environmental and medicinal applications, academics from many domains study it. Ammonium may be a biomarker of an enzyme byproduct in vital physiological processes and a natural water quality indicator. Potentiometric ion-selective electrodes (ISEs) have drawn scientific attention among classic ammonium ion detection techniques due to their cost-effectiveness, user-friendliness, and miniaturisation, which allows for convenient portable testing [13]. The highest plasma concentration of uremic toxin affects several organs and tissues directly and indirectly. Urea damages the kidneys (indirectly promoting renal fibrosis), fat cells (causing insulin resistance), blood components (causing erythropoietin carbamylation), circulatory system (CVS), and digestive tract. [14]

When assessing coffee's quality and authenticity, urea content is crucial. Various analytical methods have been used to analyse urea in food and drinks, including coffee. One common method is enzymatic assay, which uses urease to degrade urea and quantify ammonia or other reaction products [15]. Gas and high-performance liquid chromatography have also been used to measure urea in coffee samples [16]. These methods accurately measure urea levels due to their sensitivity and selectivity. FTIR and NIRS are promising methods for coffee urea analysis since they are fast and non-destructive. LC-MS has also been used to identify and quantify coffee urea [17]. These analytical methods provide academics and businesspeople several options for accurately measuring coffee samples' urea level.

2. Methodology:

The necessary reagents for the procedures consist of urease, sodium phosphate buffer, tris-acetate buffer, ethanol, glutaraldehyde, cysteamine dihydrochloride, chitosan, methanol, deionized water, 0.1 M NaCl (reference filling solution), ISAB (Internal Standard Addition Buffer), 25% glutaraldehyde solution (for the preparation of 2.5% glutaraldehyde), Nessler's reagent, tri-chloroacetic acid (TCA), and absolute ethanol. The equipment available for use includes a digital ion metre, water bath, sonicator, UV spectrophotometer, weighing balance, magnetic stirrer, and centrifuge. I would like to discuss the Ammonium ion selective electrode, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM). The experiment utilised a standard curve that correlated the concentration of NH₄⁺ with the absorbance measured at 405 nm. This allowed for the estimation of the NH₄⁺ concentration generated during the course of the experiment. In accordance with established testing protocols, a single unit of enzyme activity was defined as the amount of enzyme necessary to release 1 mole of ammonia through the hydrolysis of urea within a duration of 1 minute.

The Urease enzyme that has been previously extracted was purchased from SIGMA ALDRICH. The production and immobilisation of nano particles on a nylon membrane were conducted using the method outlined by Jakhar and Pundir in their 2017 publication [18]. The size of the urease nanoparticles was determined using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the nylon membrane were obtained prior to and following the process of immobilising urease on the membrane. These images were acquired in order to verify the successful immobilisation of urease on the nylon membrane. The Ammonium Ion Selective Electrode (AISE) was provided by Labman. The electrode was calibrated by immersing it in a 10% KCl solution for a duration of thirty minutes, followed by calibration to obtain consistent readings as per the instructions provided in the electrode manual. In accordance with the protocol proposed by Jakhar and Pundir (2017) in their research, the urea biosensor that was prepared underwent optimisation for various parameters. These parameters included pH, temperature, substrate concentration, response time, linear range, detection limit, analytical recovery, sensitivity, precision, reproducibility, storage stability, and interference from certain metabolites. A comprehensive collection of coffee powder samples was obtained from both local market vendors and online retailers. The measurement of ammonia emitted from the samples was conducted using a Labman Ammonium Ion Selective Electrode (AISE). The electrode was electrically connected to a Labman digital ion metre, which provided readings for ammonia, pH, and potential. The TISAB, equipped with a Labman electrode, was utilised in each sample to facilitate the liberation of ammonia. Please immerse the electrode in a solution consisting of 20 millilitres of alcohol and 1 cubic centimetre of TISAB.

3. Results:

3.1 Enzyme Assay:

Figure 3: Spectrophotometric graph indicating enzyme activity

The utilisation of UV-visible absorption spectroscopy in the analysis of NP aggregates has provided valuable insights into the significant structural alterations induced by the production of urease NPs. The successful formation of urease NP aggregates was facilitated by the significant changes observed in absorption peaks, as well as the enhanced absorbance within the aggregates. These factors collectively preserved the unique molecular structure of the enzyme.

3.2 Preparation of Urease Nano-Particles:

Urease nanoparticles (NPs) were synthesised through the desolvation method using ethanol at a temperature of 4°C. The aforementioned procedure effectively reduced the hydration layer enveloping urease molecules, thereby enhancing interactions such as Vander Waals, hydrophobic, and electrostatic forces. As a result, stable aggregates of urease-NP were formed. The aggregates were cross-linked using glutaraldehyde, which interacted with -NH₂ groups introduced via cysteamine dihydrochloride. This cross-linking method was employed to ensure the long-term stability and enzymatic activity of the aggregates. The urease-NP aggregates exhibited significantly enhanced enzymatic activity, potentially attributed to the increased exposure of active sites and potential structural modifications occurring during the aggregation process.

3.3 Characterization of Urease Nano-Particles:

Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) was employed to analyse the morphology and size of urease nanoparticles (NPs), as depicted in Figure 4. The urease nanoparticles exhibited a size distribution

ranging from 90 to 100 nm, with an average diameter of 96 nm. In contrast, the diameter of native monomeric urease was measured to be 13 nm using TEM in a study conducted by Turbett et al. in 1992. The results indicate that the formation of each spherical urease nanoparticle occurred through the aggregation of 14 to 18 native urease molecules.

Figure 4: FESEM Image of Urease Nanoparticles

Urease nanoparticles (NPs) were synthesised at a temperature of 4°C using the desolvation method involving ethanol. The aggregation of urease molecules was facilitated by reducing the moisture layer surrounding them, thereby enabling the occurrence of interactions such as Vander Waals forces, hydrophobic forces, and electrostatic forces. The aggregates were effectively cross-linked with glutaraldehyde, facilitated by the presence of -NH₂ groups from cysteamine dihydrochloride. This cross-linking process allowed the aggregates to maintain their structural integrity and enzymatic activity. The urease-NP aggregates exhibited a significant enhancement in enzymatic activity, potentially attributed to the increased exposure of active sites and potential structural modifications occurring during the aggregation process.

Figure 5: FTIR Graphs of Urease Nanoparticles

The figures presented in the study illustrate significant structural and chemical transformations. Curve 1 illustrates the Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrum of untreated urease within the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} . On the other hand, Curve 2 represents the FTIR spectrum of urease nanoparticles that have undergone aggregation. The key findings reveal transmittance peaks observed at 3418.61 cm^{-1} and 3410.0 cm^{-1} , which suggest the presence of –NH and –OH groups originating from cysteamine dihydrochloride. The observed peaks at 2083.78 cm^{-1} and 2079.31 cm^{-1} correspond to the stretching vibrations of N-H and C=N, respectively. The presence of vibrations at 1638.19 cm^{-1} and 1635.42 cm^{-1} indicates the occurrence of C=C stretching vibrations originating from glutaraldehyde. Additional notable peaks are observed at 1271.57 cm^{-1} and 1269.47 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the C-N stretching vibration. Furthermore, peaks at 1079.82 cm^{-1} and 1079.34 cm^{-1} are indicative of the C-O stretching vibration. Additionally, peaks at 878.53 cm^{-1} and 878.34 cm^{-1} signify the =C-H bending vibration. Lastly, the C-H and C=C bending vibrations are represented by peaks at 633.70 cm^{-1} and 627.64 cm^{-1} , respectively. The observed curves at various wavelengths demonstrate distinct bond stretching patterns, consistent with the findings reported by Jakhar and Pundir in their 2017 publication.

3.4 Characterization of Nylon Membrane by FESEM:

The FESEM images of the untreated Nylon membrane exhibited a distinctive hollow beaded structure. On the other hand, the Nylon membrane that was coated with aggregated urease nanoparticles exhibited the presence of clusters of these nanoparticles dispersed in bead-like patterns on the surface of the membrane. The present discovery confirms the attachment and immobilisation of aggregates of urease nanoparticles on the Nylon membrane.

Figure 6: FESEM Images of Nylon Membrane Before and After Immobilization of Urease Nano Particles

The enzyme that was immobilised in this manner demonstrated a retention of 86.71% of its initial activity, which was found to be comparable to that of the native enzyme. In addition, the process of conjugation resulted in a density of 1.64 mg/cm^2 . The observed outcome suggests that the enzyme activity has been enhanced due to the covalent immobilisation of urease nanoparticles onto the Nylon membrane. The utilisation of glutaraldehyde coupling was employed to couple the amino groups of cysteamine-dihydrochloride, resulting in the functionalization of urease enzyme nps for the CHIT-decorated Nylon membrane. This process facilitated the immobilisation of the enzyme.

3.5 Construction of Potentiometric Urea Biosensor:

To develop a potentiometric biosensor for the detection of urea, we utilised an ammonium ion selective electrode (AISE) in combination with a Nylon membrane that was bound with aggregates of urease nanoparticles (NPs). The biosensor setup involved the attachment of a Nylon membrane containing an aggregation of urease nanoparticles to the lower, more sensitive area of the AISE. The integrated arrangement was subsequently connected to a digital ion metre. The potentiometric response was determined using the properties of the AISE. This approach offers numerous benefits, such as a straightforward procedure, prompt response time, nondestructive examination, a wide linear range with adequate selectivity, and widespread application in quantifying various ions. In this example, a potential difference is generated over time as a result of the fluctuating concentration of NH_4^+ in the reaction buffer. The observed alteration in electrical potential is attributed to the enzymatic hydrolysis of urea by urease on the NC membrane, leading to the generation of NH_4^+ and HCO_3^- . The potential shift was measured using an ammonium ion selective electrode, specifically designed to detect NH_4^+ ions.

4. Discussion:

A study conducted by Menon and Girish in 2017 [19] utilised a designated transducer/support system for the purpose of detecting uric acid. The transducer employed in the experiment was an RB-capped TGA/GNP transducer, featuring a gold (Au) electrode. The urease enzyme was immobilised using an entrapment method. The system demonstrated a linear range for urea detection spanning from 9.90 nmol/L to 65.4 nmol/L , and

achieved a detection limit of 9.71 nmol/L. The system's storage stability was reported to be 60 days. This research provides valuable insights into a particular configuration for the detection of urea, highlighting the significance of transducer design and immobilisation techniques in the field of analytical chemistry. This study demonstrates innovation by examining the properties of commercially available coffee. Therefore, this approach can be regarded as a novel contribution. Furthermore, the websites of the aforementioned brands do not provide any such information. Although information regarding their manufacturing processes and ingredients can be found online. Numerous studies have been conducted on multiple chemical constituents present in coffee. Furthermore, numerous researchers have conducted studies on its medical significance. Urea exhibits the highest plasma concentration among uremic toxins and exerts both direct and indirect effects on multiple organs and tissues. Excessive consumption of it can potentially elevate blood toxicity levels. Therefore, this study may prove valuable in analysing the incorporation of this particular substrate into each individual cup.

5. Summary and Conclusion:

Coffee is a highly prevalent non-alcoholic caffeinated beverage, ranking second only to tea in terms of consumption. It has become an integral aspect of contemporary society. The objective of this research was to create a biosensor by immobilising the urease enzyme on a nylon membrane and subsequently attaching it to an ammonium ion selective electrode (AISE). The enzyme electrode was characterised, and it was determined that the particle sizes ranged from 0.09 μ m to 0.49 μ m in diameter. This was confirmed using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM). The biosensor demonstrated optimal response conditions at a pH of 5.5, a urea concentration of 0.05 mM in sodium phosphate buffer, and a temperature of 40°C. It exhibited a sensitivity of 38 mV/decade, an exceptionally low detection limit of 0.001 mM, and a wide linear range spanning from 0.001 to 0.80 mM. The analytical recovery of added urea exhibited a range of 98.99% to 108.35%.

This study provides insights into the chemical composition of coffee, taking into account the average urea concentration of approximately 0.133 mg/L, an average pH of 5.36, and a measured potential difference of 106.8 mV. While moderate coffee consumption has been linked to several health benefits, the precise impact of urea in coffee has not been extensively investigated. This aspect presents an interesting area for future research. In summary, the study presented herein offers significant contributions to the field through the development and characterization of a biosensor based on urease. This biosensor sheds light on the composition of coffee, a beverage that enjoys widespread consumption. The biosensor exhibits remarkable sensitivity, a low detection limit, and a wide linear range, rendering it a highly promising instrument for urea detection. Its potential applications span across diverse analytical contexts. In addition, the analytical recovery rates observed for the inclusion of urea further emphasise the dependability of the biosensor.

While there have been associations between moderate coffee consumption and various health benefits, it is necessary to conduct further research to examine the specific impact of urea in coffee. This study provides an opportunity to investigate the role of urea in coffee and its potential implications for human health. Further investigation in this field has the potential to enhance our overall comprehension of the chemical constituents of coffee and their impact on the human body. Consequently, this could provide valuable insights that can be advantageous to both coffee enthusiasts and researchers in the realm of nutrition and health.

6. Future Perspectives:

The potential application of potentiometric urea determination in coffee, which utilises urease enzymes and ion-selective electrodes (ISEs), shows great potential for the future. The implementation of this technology will enhance quality control practises within the coffee industry, thereby strengthening consumer confidence and promoting compliance with rigorous food safety regulations. With the continuous advancement of technology, it is reasonable to anticipate improvements and cost-effective enhancements. The implementation of automation has the potential to optimise the process, while also aligning with sustainability initiatives due to its eco-friendly characteristics. Furthermore, the versatility and potential impact of this technology in assessing a wide range of quality parameters highlight its significance for the future of the coffee industry.

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